

The Impact of Work Motivation and Engagement on the Productivity: Case Study at Consumer Loan Account Officer

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ABSTRACT: Consumer credit has emerged as the type of credit that leads most banks in Indonesia, including Bank Batara, which has made consumer credit the first pillar of its credit operation. However, taking into account the situations that have come about in the recent few periods, the quantity of consumer loan disbursement at Bank Batara genuinely reveals a minor average benefit in distribution compared to rival banks, despite the fact that the characteristics and credit terms offered remain largely the same, which suggests the differences in productivity issues within consumer credit divisions, particularly account officer productivity at Bank Batara.

The present study seeks to evaluate the effect of job motivation and employee engagement on employee work productivity. This study makes use of linear analytic methodologies to verify the hypothesis given. The findings gathered suggest that all variables are in dire straits. Partially, job motivation and employee engagement have a favourable and profound effect on employee work productivity. Likewise, simultaneously, job motivation and employee engagement have an enormous impact on employee work productivity.

KEYWORDS: employee work productivity multiple linear regression analysis, work engagement, work motivation.

INTRODUCTION

Consumer loans are a prominent product in the banking business. Consumer loans are a vital part of the Indonesian banking business, providing consumers with access to capital for covering their personal and family costs. Consumer credit products are one of the items that contribute the most to Batara Bank's profits; they make up 60% of the bank's credit portfolio, with their market segment being public servants. In the organisational structure, Batara Bank is separated across two distinct areas, namely business and support. The frontline in marketing credit consumer products is an account officer that is encompassed within the business category with a job description of executing marketing, development, and coaching of the consumer credit business segment along with monthly evaluations in accordance with pertinent regulations through implementing the principle of prudence to accomplish the business targets that have been set.

In the banking business, productivity refers to the efficiency and effectiveness with which banks and financial institutions use their resources to create output or value-added services. Productivity is a key aspect of the performance of banks, as it assists in optimising the use of resources while maintaining the quality of the services supplied.

Work motivation drives and encourages employees to be able to carry out their individual jobs by accomplishing goals with full awareness, passion, and responsibility (Anoraga, 2014). This illustrates that job motivation gives birth to passion or work drive. Therefore, job motivation in psychology tends to be a morale booster. Robust and poor work motivation in a workforce also influences the magnitude of their successes or output. Meanwhile, Gruman & Saks (2011) stated that employee engagement influences total employee productivity and is the key to organisational success and profitability, which may boost employee performance, retain people, and provide happiness and success for the firm. Thus, the purpose of this present study is to look into the impact of motivation and employee engagement on the productivity of Batara Bank consumer credit account officers.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Work Motivation

Motivation is a desire in a person causing the person to perform an action. A person takes action for something in achieving a goal (Mathis & Jackson, 2009). Therefore, motivation is a driver that leads to goals and it rarely comes to naught. Motivation as a process

that describes the intensity, direction and persistence of effort to achieve a goal. Based on the above understandings, motivation can be defined as an action to influence others to behave regularly (Robbins & Judge, 2013).

Motivation is the provision of driving force that creates a person's work excitement, so that they want to work together, work effectively and are integrated with all efforts to achieve satisfaction (Hasibuan, 2019). Motivation can also be interpreted as a driving force that causes someone to want to give up abilities in the form of expertise or skills possessed, energy and time that have become responsibilities and obligations for the achievement of goals and various organizational goals that have been determined before. In line with this, Work motivation is a model in moving and directing employees to be able to carry out their respective duties in achieving goals with full awareness, enthusiasm and responsibility (Anoraga, 2014). This shows that work motivation gives rise to enthusiasm or work drive. Therefore, work motivation in psychology is commonly called a morale booster. Strong and weak work motivation of a workforce also determines the size of his achievement.

Employee Engagement

Employee engagement was first proposed by a Gallup research group (Endress & Smoak, 2008). They claim that employee engagement can predict improved employee performance, profitability, employee retention, customer satisfaction, and success for the organization (Bates, 2004). The word engage has various meanings and many researchers have different meanings of engagement (Albrecht, 2010). When the individual cares deeply about what he does and is committed to doing it to the best of his ability, he will feel compelled to do rather than just stand still. This is part of engagement. Employee engagement is the passion of organizational members for their work where they work and express themselves physically, cognitively, and emotionally during work (Albrecht, 2010).

A different definition is expressed by Thomas in (Henryhand, 2009) who states that employee engagement is represented as a two-way relationship between employees and organizations where these two parties are aware of each other's needs and work together to meet those needs. Another definition according to (Schaufeli et al., 2022) engagement is defined as positive, meaningful, and motivational things characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption. Vigor is characterized by high energy levels, resilience, willingness to try, and not giving up in the face of challenges. Dedication is characterized by feeling valuable, enthusiastic, inspiring, valuable and challenging, and finally absorption is characterized by full concentration on a task.

Work Productivity

Productivity can be evaluated based on an employee's performance over a period of time. The productivity of a particular employee is usually measured against the average of employees doing similar jobs. It can also be evaluated according to the quantity of units of product or service processed by the employee within a defined time frame. Employee productivity has become an important goal for companies, as the success of an organization largely depends on it (Gordon, 2009).

(Gordon, 2009) also showed that aligning strategic vision with employee productivity contributes significantly to organizational success. This alignment can motivate and inspire employees to be more creative and ultimately improve their performance effectiveness in achieving organizational goals and objectives (Morales et al., 2008). Moreover, higher productivity tends to increase competitive

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The quantitative technique was applied in the present study. The research design executed in the present study is a conclusive design that tries to examine particular hypotheses and specific relationships. The data analysis techniques employed in this study include descriptive analysis of respondent replies, validity and reliability tests, classical assumption testing, and multiple linear regression analysis.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The following presents the findings of the descriptive analysis of respondents' responses, classical assumption tests, multiple linear regression analysis, and hypothesis testing.

Result

Descriptive Analysis

According to the findings of respondent descriptive data processing, the three variables are included in an extremely low criterion based on the continuum line. This may be seen in Figures 1, 2, and 3. The Work Motivation condition has an average score of 3.06; hence, it is included in the "Low enough" category. This may be illustrated on the continuum as follows:

Figure 1. Work Motivation Continuum

The state of Employee Engagement of AO Consumer Credit products from the perspective of respondents has an average score of 3.02, which means that it is included in the "Not Conforming" category. This correlates with the continuum presented in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2. Employee Engagement Continuum

The state of respondents' Work Productivity placed it at an average score of 3.05, which signifies it was in the category of "Quite Low". This is consistent with the continuum illustrated in Figure 4.3.

Figure 3. Work Productivity Continuum

Classical Assumption Test

Normality Test Result

The normality test can be seen on the *Normal Probability Plot* graph as shown in Figure 4 below.

Figure 4. Normal P-Plot Graph

From the graph in Figure 4 above, it can be seen that the data is spread around the diagonal line, hence it can be deduced that the data is near to the normal distribution.

Multicollinearity Test

The multicollinearity test can be seen in the *Coefficients* table as in Table 1 below.

Table 1.Table *Coefficients*

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Correlations			Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Zero-order	Partial	Part	Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	-.064	.161		-.401	.689					
	X1	.276	.091	.234	3.021	.003	.819	.267	.123	.277	3.611
	X2	.750	.084	.689	8.904	.000	.888	.632	.362	.277	3.611

a. Dependent Variable: Y

According to Table 1, the value of the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) for all variables is less than five, implying that there is no multicollinearity amongst the variables examined.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Figure 5 presents the heteroscedasticity test in the Scatterplot Table.

Figure 5. Scatterplot

Based on Figure 5, it can be observed that the data is distributed around the number 0 (zero) on the Y axis and does not create a definite pattern; hence, it can be stated that heteroscedasticity is not present in the study data.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Multiple linear regression analysis is used by researchers to process research data using SPSS software. Based on the results of data processing, multiple linear regression model coefficients are derived for each variable, as contained in Table 1.

Table 1. Regression Model

Coefficients ^a												
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Correlations			Collinearity Statistics		
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Zero-order	Partial	Part	Tolerance	VIF	
1	(Constant)	-.064	.161		-.401	.689						
	X1	.276	.091	.234	3.021	.003	.819	.267	.123	.277	3.611	
	X2	.750	.084	.689	8.904	.000	.888	.632	.362	.277	3.611	

a. Dependent Variable: Y

Table 1 illustrates the regression equation to determine the constant number and the coefficients for each study variable. Based on Table 1, the formulation for regression equation is as follow.

$$Y = 0.276 X_1 + 0.750 X_2 - 0.064 + e$$

Where,

- Y = Work Productivity
- X₁ = Work Motivation
- X₂ = Employee Engagement
- e = error

Coefficient of Determination

The results of deriving the coefficient of determination through SPSS software are presented in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Model Summary

Model Summary ^a											
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson	
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change		
1	.896 ^b	.803	.799	.32852	.803	242.211	2	119	.000	2.115	

a. Predictors: (Constant), X2, X1
b. Dependent Variable: Y

Table 2 exhibits the amount of the coefficient of determination, which assists in determining the extent of the variability of dependent variables that may be explained by the independent variables. The value of R-square, or the coefficient of determination, for the resulted empirical model, which incorporated the variables Work Motivation (X1) and employee engagement (X2), reached the level of 80,3%. Furthermore, this may imply that 80.3% of the work productivity (Y) that occurs may be explained by the variables Work Motivation (X 1) and Employee Engagement (X 2). The remaining 19.7% (100%–80.3%) is explained by factors and other causal variables.

Hypotheses Test

According to Table 1, the significant values of the Work Motivation variable (X1) and Employee Engagement variable (X2) are 0.003 and 0.000, respectively. This number is less than 0.05 (0.05), implying that Work Motivation and Employee Engagement have a minor impact on Work Productivity. Motivation is the provision of a propelling force that generates a person's work enthusiasm so that they want to work together, work effectively, and are incorporated with all efforts to achieve satisfaction (Hasibuan, 2019). A person is intrinsically motivated when he performs activities or works voluntarily without expectation of any material reward or external reason (Bhaduri & Kumar, 2009). Motivation may also be interpreted as a driving force that causes someone to want to give up abilities in the form of expertise or skills possessed, energy, and time that have become responsibilities and obligations for the achievement of goals and various organisational goals that have been determined before. In line with this, Anoraga (2014) stated that work motivation is a model for moving and directing employees to be able to carry out their respective duties in achieving objectives with complete awareness, enthusiasm, and responsibility. This demonstrates that work motivation gives rise to enthusiasm or work desire. Therefore, work motivation in psychology is commonly termed a morale stimulant. Strong and feeble work motivation in a workforce also determines the magnitude of his achievement. Laksmiari (22019) conducted research, with the results demonstrating that work motivation influences employee productivity. Employee engagement is associated with enhanced employee performance, profitability, employee retention, customer satisfaction, and success for the organisation (Bates, 2004). When the individual cares profoundly about what he does and is committed to doing it to the best of his ability, he will feel compelled to do something rather than just remain still. This is part of engagement. Employee engagement is the passion of organisational members for their work, where they work and express themselves physically, cognitively, and emotionally during work (Albrecht, 2010). (Dayyan et al., 2019; Dinillah & Sabil, 2022) conducted research, with the results confirming that employee engagement has an influence on employee work productivity. The research that researchers do uses distinct dimensions. The results of the F test can be seen in Table 3. From the table, a significant value of 0.000 (< 0.05) is obtained. As a result, H 0 is rejected and H 1 is approved, implying that there is a considerable effect between the variables of Work Motivation and Employee Engagement on productivity at exactly the same time.

Table 3. ANOVA

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	52.292	2	26.141	242.211	.000 ^b
	Residual	12.843	119	.108		
	Total	65.125	121			

a. Dependent Variable: Y
b. Predictors: (Constant), X2, X1

DISCUSSION

Business Solution Regarding Work Motivation

The descriptive study analysis results are employed for recognizing business difficulties that arise in the Work Motivation variable to ensure it may be used as a reference in enhancing Work Productivity. Regional Office I, AO Consumer Credit. The following are the three statement items with the lowest score:

1. The lowest statement was the tenth statement, in which respondents were dissatisfied with their current employment, which was extremely challenging. More individuals state that they detest their jobs and that they are not challenging. This is the case because AO Consumer Credit has become overwhelmed with the objectives and cadence of work assigned to them, and they resent what they do. In light of this conclusion, the Consumer Credit Division ought to reconfigure the new consumer credit goal plan for the Account

Officer to provide opportunities for the Account Officer to make this challenging task easier, new and thrilling to do. For example, if AO transmits other banking products to associated work divisions and the goal is met (closure), the achievements can be transformed into a reduction in the remaining AO target.

2. The second-lowest statement is the fifth statement, namely that respondents feel that the company's advice on rewards and incentives does not drive respondents to work enthusiastically. At the bank where respondents work, consumer credit is the first pillar of trade. However, the amount of incentive earned is not more than that obtained by other credit segments, especially when compared to the supporting part.

3. The third-lowest statement is the third statement, in which respondents say that a lack of money to get honors, recognition, or job progression in their line of work pushes them to work harder. This is due to the fact that there is no difference in appreciation between business and supporting work units, despite the fact that the risk of business unit work is larger than that of supporting. Furthermore, prospects for promotion are not distinguished between business and support work divisions. As a result, the Human Capital Division should assess the performance appraisal system between business and supporting work units according to their relative risks.

Business Solution About Employee Engagement

The result of the descriptive research analysis is deployed to ascertain business challenges that emerge in the Employee Engagement variable, which in the future may be used as a reference to strengthen Work productivity in AO Consumer Credit in Regional Office I. The three statements with the lowest scores are as follows:

1. The lowest statement (1st statement), particularly spoke of how respondents find it difficult to disengage from work. More respondents said that they have no difficulty disengaging from their jobs. This happens because AO Consumer Credit has not fully integrated their work into the daily routine, nor has it made their profession a career that they are passionate about. In connection with this issue, the Consumer Credit Division ought to reinvigorate the product and execute training and skill development in order to increase AO's interest in his work.

2. The second and third lowest statements (2nd and 3rd statement) spoke of how respondents experience less content when they start doing their work and do it intensely. This indicates that people are less engaged in their jobs. In reality, respondents' jobs take up more than half a day of their everyday lives.

Business Solution Regarding Work Productivity

The result of the descriptive research analysis is deployed to ascertain business challenges that emerge in the Work Productivity variable, which in the future may be used as a reference to strengthen Work productivity in AO Consumer Credit in Regional Office I. The three statements with the lowest scores are as follows:

1. The lowest statements, the 5th and 6th, indicate that respondents are able to optimize and maximize the use of current resources to assist the attainment of work aims and do not face substantial hurdles while working. More respondents assessed that they were less able to optimize their resources. This is because it is tough for AO Consumer Credit to come up with fresh concepts to meet its high work objectives. In this sense, the Consumer Credit Division should convene a focus group discussion that addresses what AO's challenges are and how solutions can be found to accomplish work targets by maximizing the performance of existing resources while still maintaining the concept of efficiency.

2. The third-lowest statement of the third statement is that respondents believe they are less capable of meeting the specified work time objective, so they do not require extra time and are fairly composed at the end of the assessment period. This exemplifies a work goal that is so demanding that the vast majority of respondents lack the ability to meet it. In this regard, the Consumer Credit Division ought to coordinate with the Director of Consumer and Retail to assess the target amount imposed on their Account Officer.

CONCLUSION

The conclusions of the present study are as follows.

- 1) The three variables are included in very low criterion based on the continuum line.
- 2) Partially Work Motivation has a favorable and considerable effect on Work Productivity.
- 3) Partially Employee Engagement has a favorable and considerable effect on Work Productivity

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